

Research Article

Health Impact of Heavy Metals in Quarry Dust On Quarry Workers in Osun State, Nigeria

Jooda Kehine Olurotimi¹, Ano-Edward Gbemi Henry^{1*}, Ododo Benard Itopa², Uduagbamen Peter Kehinde³, Ajao I. Oluwaseyi⁴, Lasisi Mathew Eniola¹, Onabanjo Blessing Dupe¹, Famoroti Busayo Mercy¹ and Oladipo Elijah Kolawole⁵

¹The Faculty of Basic Clinical sciences, Bowen University Iwo/Bowen Teaching hospital, Ogbomoso, Nigeria

²Division of Radiology, Department of Surgery, Federal University/Federal University Teaching Hospital, Lokoja, Nigeria

³Division of Nephrology and Hypertension, Department of Internal Medicine, Bowen University/Bowen University Teaching Hospital, Ogbomosho, Nigeria

⁴Department of Statistics, Federal Polytechnic, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

⁵Department of Microbiology, Laboratory of Molecular Biology, Immunology and Bioinformatics, Adeleke University, Osun State, Nigeria

*Corresponding author: gbemi.ano-edward@bowen.edu.ng

Article Info

Keywords: Quarry site, heavy metals, renal function, inflammatory cells.

Received: 07.07.2025

Accepted: 17.08.2025

Published: 25.08.2025

 © 2025 by the author's. The terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license apply to this open access article.

Abstract

Quarrying exposes host people to risks to their health as they may be exposed to high levels of heavy metals. This case controlled study investigated the impact of heavy metals found in quarry dusts on the health of quarry workers in a community. The study involved 100 quarry workers and 100 healthy participants both males and females. Random purposive sampling was used and majority of the participants fell in the age range of 41-60 years. A significant amount of the tests participants had secondary and tertiary form of education. Despite their high level of education about 77% of the participants had worked in the quarry for a period of 6-10 years. The total protein, SGOT, SGPT, and alkaline phosphatase were significantly raised among the tests group a $p=0.0001$, while albumin was moderately reduced in tests group, $p=0.0001$. Although, the PCV, WBC, and neutrophil count in the test group were significantly reduced, the counts of lymphocytes and eosinophils were raised. The values of urea and creatinine were also significantly raised at $p=0.0001$. All the workers in different areas of the company were exposed to a high level of lead, nickel and chromium, 0.54 mg/kg, 0.61 mg/kg, and 0.13 mg/kg respectively. In addition, more inflammatory cells, tubule epithelial cells, transition cells and yeast cells were more common in the urine of tests participants. The high concentration of lead, nickel and chromium has begun to have an effect on the health of the quarry workers. There is a need for further intervention by health authorities and the quarry-site owners to avoid further deterioration in the health status of the workers.

1. Introduction

Quarry mining processes, cause metal pollution of the soil, water, and vegetation around quarry operation zones. A number of elements have been linked to occupational exposure in quarries. They include manganese, copper, zinc, and arsenic. Quarrying exposes host people to risks to their health and the environment because of its complex and precise interactions with the environment. Thus, there is a rising concern about possible exposure to heavy metals globally due to their extensive usage in solid mineral exploration, mining, public infrastructure construction, industries, and metal technologies, as well as a substantial growth in their worldwide production. According to [1], environmental pollution from quarrying, sandblasting, and the emission of hazardous chemicals kills close to 4 million people annually

in underdeveloped countries. Recognizing the harmful effects of quarrying activities on the health of the quarry workers and residents of the towns where the quarries are situated is essential, as they may be exposed to high levels of heavy metals due to the leaching of heavy metals into groundwater, surface water, and ambient air from mining activities and they may not be aware of it [2].

Employees are exposed when they inhale dust, eat or drink contaminated food, or come into touch with infected materials via their skin while doing their routine job activities. The concentration of the metals is typically a determining factor in toxicity and the consequent damage that environmental toxins bring to human health, as reported by [3]. Although, exposure to metallic contaminants from quarry sites may pose health hazards, there is a dearth of studies on the consequences on the health of Osun State quarry workers. This study aims to determine the impact of heavy metals in quarry dusts on the health status of quarry workers in Awo a village in Egbedore Local Government Areas in Osun State, South-West Nigeria.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Design and location

Study Design

The prospective case controlled study was carried out in Awo village, a rural hamlet in the Awo-Egbedore local government area of Osun State, southwest Nigeria. There were 100 cases and 100 controls who were eligible for the study and gave informed consent.

Study Population

All the participants were eighteen years old or more. Two hundred volunteers were recruited for the test, with the control group consisting of forty females and sixty males, and the test group consisting of 90 males and 10 females. Each participant completed a well-structured questionnaire that was designed from the Occupational Safety and Health Administration [4] and used to gather information about their sociodemographic traits. Those who could not fill the questionnaire were assisted. In this study, random purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the participants. Before the blood and urine samples were taken, informed consent was given by the participants.

Inclusion Criteria for cases

Quarry-site workers who are above 18 years old, with minimum of five to six years of service within the quarry site and are willing to give consent.

Exclusion Criteria

Quarry-site workers less than 18 years old, those that did not give consent and those that have not worked up to five years. Workers that have other underlying health condition as provided in the questionnaire.

Inclusion Criteria for controls

Those that are medically fit, above 18 years old, and do not live nearby or work in the quarry sites.

Exclusion criteria for controls

For controls: Those that are above 18 years of age, living nearby quarry site and those with medical ailments.

2.2. Study technique

Preparation of questionnaire

A pre-tested questionnaire was adapted from the Occupational Safety and Health Administration [4]. The format was used to enter the data, which included the socio-demography, history of exposure to cement, smoking, the use of safety gadgets, general health, past and present medical history, including possible occupational hazards [4]. Random purposive sampling approach was used to pick participants who met the inclusion criteria for both the case and control studies. The study was described to the participants, and an informed consent was obtained before filling the questionnaire.

Minimum Sample Size Determination

The minimum sample size was calculated using the formula of [5] and stated as follows:

$$N = \frac{Z^2XP(1-P)}{d^2}$$

N = Minimum sample size

P = Prevalence of heavy metal toxicity in Nigeria = 0.094 (9.4%) [6].

d = Desired level of significance = 0.05 (5%)

Z = Confidence interval = 1.96 (95% confidence interval)

$$N = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.094(1-0.094)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$N = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.085164}{0.0025}$$

$$N = 130$$

Though the minimum sample size is 130. However, 100 quarry workers and 100 apparently healthy non-quarry workers' subjects were recruited as control and thus making a total of 200 subjects recruited for the study.

Study Duration

This study lasted six months, beginning with the filling of the questionnaire, sample collection and statistical analysis.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval was received from the Ethics and Research Committee of the Ministry of Health, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria. The reference number is OSHREC/PRS/569T/219. Permission was also granted by the administrators of the quarry site. Written informed consent was obtained from eligible participants after they had been well educated on the objectives and format of the study. Confidentiality was duly observed as each participant's personally-identifiable information was altered, and participants' medical history, clinical and laboratory findings were anonymized. The standards governing confidentiality and privacy were followed.

2.3. Sample Collection

Blood sample collection

The trial participants provided a venous blood sample of ten millilitres after an overnight fast lasting between ten and twelve hours. The blood sample was divided into four millilitres (4 ml) for the lithium heparine tube, two millilitres for plain tubes, and four millilitres for an EDTA bottle. After centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 5 minutes, the separated serum was stored at -20°C until the experiment was performed. The testing parameters included tests for liver enzymes, electrolytes, urea, and creatinine.

3. Laboratory Analysis

3.1. Liver Enzymes Estimation

Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT): ALT activity was assessed using the enzymatic method with a Randox ALT kit (Product No: 05055273200188). The enzyme catalyzes the transamination of L-alanine and α -ketoglutarate to yield pyruvate and L-glutamate. In the presence of NADH and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), pyruvate is further reduced to L-lactate, resulting in the oxidation of NADH to NAD^+ . The reaction was monitored spectrophotometrically by measuring the decrease in absorbance at 340 nm.

In practice, 10 μL of serum was added to 200 μL of R1 reagent and incubated 37°C for 5 minutes. Subsequently, 50 μL of R2 reagent was added, and the mixture was incubated for an additional minute. Absorbance was recorded at 405 nm at one-minute intervals for three minutes. ALT activity was calculated by comparing the change in absorbance per minute ($\delta A/\text{min}$) to that of a calibrator. [7].

3.2. Aspartate Amino Transferase Estimation(AST)

Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST): AST activity was determined using the Randox AST kit (Product No: 05055273200409). The assay is based on the AST-mediated transamination of L-aspartate and α -ketoglutarate to produce oxaloacetate and L-glutamate. Oxaloacetate is reduced to malate by malate dehydrogenase (MDH) in the presence of NADH, and the corresponding decrease in NADH concentration is measured at 340 nm.

200 μL of R1 and 50 μL of R2 were dispensed into test, standard, and blank cuvettes for the assay. Then, 10 μL of sample was added to the test cuvette, and 10 μL of standard reagent was added to the standard. Following incubation at 37°C , absorbance readings were taken at 405 nm.

3.3. Urea and Creatinine test

Urea estimation: Urea levels were measured using the enzymatic Berthelot method. Urease hydrolyses urea into ammonia and carbon dioxide. The released ammonia reacts with alkaline hypochlorite and sodium salicylate in the presence of sodium nitroprusside to form a green-colored indophenol complex, which is quantified at 600 nm.

A working reagent was prepared by combining one part R1 with twenty-four parts R2. One millilitre of the working reagent was added to each tube (blank, standard, and test), followed by 10 μL of standard or sample. After mixing and incubating at 37°C for 5 minutes, 1 mL of R3 was added, and the tubes were incubated under the same conditions. Absorbance was measured at 600 nm [7].

3.4. Creatinine Estimation

Creatinine estimation: The Jaffe reaction estimated creatinine concentration. Creatinine reacts with picric acid in an alkaline solution to form a red-orange chromogen whose absorbance is measured at 505 nm.

In the assay, 10 μL of serum was mixed with 200 μL of R1 reagent and incubated at 37°C for 5 minutes. Subsequently, 50 μL of R2 reagent was added, mixed, and incubated for one minute. Absorbance was measured at 505 nm at one-minute intervals for three minutes. The

$\delta A/\text{min}$ was calculated to determine creatinine concentration relative to a calibrator [7].

3.5. Haematological Analysis

Haematological parameters were analysed using an automated haematology analyser based on fluid dynamics and impedance principles. After lysing red blood cells, the remaining leukocytes and reticulocytes pass through the detection chamber individually via sheath flow. Simultaneous measurements of cell volume, conductivity, and light scatter enable classification of blood cell populations [8].

3.6. Cytological Staining

Papanicolaou Staining: This staining method differentiates between acidophilic and basophilic cell structures and enhances nuclear morphology. Smears were fixed with a cytological fixative for 30 minutes, stained with Harris hematoxylin for 4 minutes, rinsed with tap water, and differentiated in 1% acid alcohol. Dehydration was performed using 80%, 70%, and 50% ethanol, followed by bluing in tap water for 10 minutes. Smears were then passed through 70% and 95% ethanol, stained with OG6 for 2 minutes, rinsed twice in 95% ethanol, stained with EA50 for 2 minutes, rinsed again in 95% ethanol, dehydrated in absolute alcohol, cleared in xylene, and mounted using DPX [9].

3.7. May Grunwald-Giemsa

Smears were air dried and treated in May-Grumwald stain for 5 minutes, then transferred to Giemsa stains and allowed to stand for 10 minutes. The smears were later rinsed in buffer with pH 6.8 and 50/50 buffer/acetone respectively. The smears were subsequently dehydrated in acetone and cleared in xylene [10].

3.8. Estimation of Heavy Metals (Chromium, Nickel and Lead)

The concentrations of Nickel, Chromium, and Lead in soil dust samples were determined using atomic absorption spectrophotometry. In this method, 0.5 mL of concentrated sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), 1 mL of perchloric acid (HClO₄), and 5 mL of concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃) were added to 1 g of the dust sample in a 100 mL beaker. The mixture was vigorously stirred, then brought to a gentle boil and evaporated on a hot plate until the volume reduced to about 5 mL, just before precipitation occurred. The solution was then transferred to a 25 mL volumetric flask and topped up to the mark after cooling. A portion of this thoroughly mixed solution was used for metal determination. Analysis of the digested soil samples was conducted using a Buck Scientific model PG 990 Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer [11].

3.9. Data Analysis

The data was analysed using IBM's Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0. The variables were expressed as means \pm standard deviations. The independent t-test was used to compare mean testosterone and oestrogen levels between quarry workers and healthy controls. The significance level was chosen at $P < 0.05$.

4. Results

This study included a total of 200 participants, 100 in the test group and 100 in the control group. There were 90 males and 10 female tests participants. While 60 males and 40 females were the control participants. The majority of the participants fell within the 41-60 age range (table 1). About (77.0%) of the participants had worked in the quarry between 6-10 years (table 2). Almost all the participants had a formal education (table 3). There was a statistically significant increase in total protein, SGOT, SGPT, Alkaline Phosphatase among the test groups at $p=0.0001$. While, Albumin significantly decreased in the Test groups when compared to control groups at $p=0.0001$ (Table 4).

There was statistically significance decreased in PCV, WBC count, Neutrophil in Test groups at $p=0.0001$ and, a corresponding increase in lymphocytes, and eosinophils (table 5). Urea and creatinine significantly increased in Test groups when compared to the Control groups at $p < 0.05$ (Table 6). The mean concentration for lead, nickel and chromium of 0.54 mg/kg, 0.61 mg/kg, and 0.13 mg/kg respectively, were above the normal limit (table 7). There were more inflammatory cells, tubule epithelial cells, transitional cells and yeast cells in the test group than in the control group (table 8). The age group 41-60 years had most of the inflammatory cells, tubule epithelial cells, transition cells and yeast cells (table 9).

Table 1: Distribution of Quarry and non-quarry workers According to their Age Groups.

Age (Years old)	Quarry workers (%) N=100	Non quarry workers N=100 (%)	P-value
21-40	36 (36.0)	46 (46.0)	0.190
41-60	47 (47.0)	43 (43.0)	
61-80	14 (14.0)	11 (11.0)	
81-100	3 (3.0)	0 (0.0)	

(*) means statistically significance at $p < 0.05$.

Table 2: Frequency of Number of Years of Exposure (Working in Quarry Company).

Duration of exposure	Number Tested	Quarry workers	P-Value
	n=100	n=100 (%)	
6-10years	77	77 (77.0)	0.0001*
11-15years	8	8 (8.0)	
≥16 years	15	15 (15.0)	

(*) means statistically significance at $p < 0.05$.

Table 3: Distribution of Quarry and non-quarry workers According to their Educational status

Educational Status	Quarry workers (%)	Non quarry workers (%)	P-value
No Formal Education	0 (0.0)	2 (2.0)	0.0002*
Primary	36 (36.0)	19 (19.0)	
Secondary	42 (42.0)	30 (30.0)	
Tertiary	22 (22.0)	49 (49.0)	

(*) means statistically significance at $p < 0.05$.

Table 4: Liver Function Tests in Test Groups (Quarry workers) and Control Groups (Non-Quarry workers)

Parameters	Test groups	Control groups	P-value
	(Mean ± S.E.M)	(Mean ± S.E.M)	
Total Protein (g/L)	81.58±1.40	65.30±0.187	0.0001*
Albumin (g/L)	24.12±0.505	40.18±0.536	0.0001*
SGOT (IU/L)	25.28±0.300	9.39±0.517	0.0001*
SGPT (IU/L)	28.43±0.338	12.13±0.470	0.0001*
Alkaline Phosphatase (IU/L)	31.97±1.114	23.03±0.693	0.0001*

(*) means statistically significance at $p < 0.05$.

Table 5: Full Blood Counts in Test Groups (Quarry workers) and Control Groups (Non-Quarry workers)

Parameters	Test groups	Control groups	P-value
	(Mean ± S.E.M)	(Mean ± S.E.M)	
PCV (%)	33.04±0.280	42.53±0.330	0.0001*
WBC count (10 ⁹ /L)	3.23±0.071	6.85±0.174	0.0001*
Neutrophil (%)	34.44±0.761	58.53±0.745	0.0001*
Lymphocytes (%)	57.43±0.672	39.31±0.697	0.0001*
Eosinophil (%)	7.09±0.240	2.00±0.167	0.0001*

(*) means statistically significance at $p < 0.05$.

Table 6: Kidney Function Tests in Test Groups (Quarry workers) and Control Groups (Non-Quarry workers)

Parameters	Test groups	Control groups	P-value
	(Mean ± S.E.M)	(Mean ± S.E.M)	
Urea (mg/dL)	53.78±0.645	28.50±0.997	0.0001*
Creatinine (mg/dL)	2.927±0.0346	1.015±0.0333	0.0001*

(*) means statistically significance at $p < 0.05$.

Table 9: Comparison of cell types based on the age groups of quarry workers

Cell Types	Number Tested	21-40 years	41-60 years	61-80 years	81-100 years	P-Value
Inflammatory cells	75	23 (30.7)	41 (54.7)	11 (14.7)	0 (0.0)	0.0001*
Tubule epithelial cell	60	20 (33.3)	28 (46.7)	12 (20.0)	0 (0.0)	0.0001*
Transitional epithelial cells	60	22 (36.7)	38 (63.3)	10 (16.7)	1 (1.7)	0.0001*
Calcium Oxalate	10	2 (20.0)	4 (40.0)	3 (30.0)	1 (10.0)	0.572
Yeast cells	20	5 (25.0)	9 (45.0)	4 (20.0)	2 (10.0)	0.157
Intermediate epithelial cells	10	3 (30.0)	5 (50.0)	2 (20.0)	0 (0.0)	0.158
Squamous epithelial cells	70	24 (34.3)	33 (47.1)	11 (15.7)	2 (2.9)	0.0001*

(*) means statistically significance at $p < 0.05$.

Table 7: Concentration of Harmful Dust Elements(metals)

Working area	Lead (normal 0.05mg/kg)	Nickel (normal 0.05mg/kg)	Chromium (normal 0.05mg/kg)
Crusher	1.322	1.190	0.082
Mechanic shop	1.119	1.124	0.097
Administrative office	0.087	0.080	0.083
Waiting area	0.098	0.092	0.288
Gate house	0.073	0.550	0.103
Mean Value	0.54	0.61	0.13

Table 8: Different cell types seen in the urine of Test groups (quarry workers) and Control groups (non-quarry workers)

Cell Types	Test groups	Control groups	P-value
	n=100 (%)	n=100 (%)	
Inflammatory cells			
Yes	75 (75.0)	0 (0.0)	0.001*
No	25 (25.0)	100 (100.0)	
Tubule epithelial cells			
Yes	60 (60.0)	0 (0.0)	0.001*
No	40 (40.0)	100 (100.0)	
Transitional epithelial cells			
Yes	60 (60.0)	0 (0.0)	0.001*
No	40 (40.0)	100 (100.0)	
Calcium Oxalate			
Yes	10 (10.0)	10 (10.0)	1.000
No	90 (90.0)	90 (90.0)	
Yeast cells			
Yes	20 (20.0)	15 (15.0)	0.352
No	80 (80.0)	85 (85.0)	
Intermediate epithelial cells			
Yes	10 (10.0)	50 (50.0)	0.001*
No	90 (90.0)	50 (50.0)	
Squamous epithelial cells			
Yes	70 (70.0)	70 (70.0)	1.000
No	30 (30.0)	30 (30.0)	

(*) means statistically significance at $p < 0.05$.

5. Discussion

In this study, more than half of the quarry workers had 6-10 years of experience, making up 77.0% of the cohort, which is consistent with the findings of [12]. It means a large number of the workforce have had prolonged exposure to quarry dust which can significantly impact their health and increase the risk of adverse health outcomes as reported by [13, 14]. Long-term exposure to quarry work can also lead to a range of other health issues, such as silicosis which is a respiratory disease caused by inhaling silica dust generated during quarrying activities [15]. Other disorders, that can be associated with long-term exposure to heavy machinery and equipment includes musculoskeletal disorders, hearing loss due to noise pollution, and injuries from accidents, all of which can significantly impact the physical well-being of quarry workers over time [16]. Prolonged exposure has also been linked with increased stress, anxiety, and depression. Socioeconomically, the effect of years of exposure to quarry work extends beyond individual health outcomes to impact workers' financial stability and social standing. [17], discovered that long-term exposure may limit career mobility and opportunities for skill development, trapping workers in low-wage, and precarious employment, especially in resource-limited settings like ours. These workers face socioeconomic disparities which is prevalent in the quarry industry, including inadequate access to healthcare and lack of job security, and these can exacerbate the vulnerabilities faced by workers with prolonged exposure.

The current study identified variations in heavy metal concentrations among quarry workers with occupational exposure, raising significant concerns about their health. The Occupational Safety and Health Administration [4] specifies normal concentration values for lead, nickel, and chromium at 0.05 mg/kg each [18]. However, analysis of the dust samples from the quarry environments in our study indicated significantly higher concentrations of these hazardous elements with lead, nickel, and chromium, having average concentrations of 0.54 mg/kg, 0.61 mg/kg, and 0.13 mg/kg, respectively. Thus, surpassing the limits set by the Occupational Safety and Health Administration [4]. A clear indication that the workers are exposed to high levels and, face serious health risks, which includes kidney failure, effect on their hematological profile, respiratory problems, skin disorder, neurological damage, and cognitive impairments ([19, 20]).

In this study, total Protein (TP) levels showed a substantial increase in quarry workers compared to the control groups. A similar finding was made by [21]. This elevation suggests a potential disruption in protein metabolism, possibly due to the presence of harmful substances in the quarry environment. Such disturbances in protein metabolism can have cascading effects on various physiological processes within the liver. Similarly, there was a significant decrease in albumin levels in quarry workers. This agrees with study by [22] and it is an indication of liver dysfunction or injury, since albumin is primarily synthesized in the liver. Albumin is the most abundant protein synthesized by the

liver, it is essential for maintaining colloidal osmotic pressure and transporting various substances in the blood. Thus, a reduction in the level of albumin could lead to oedema in interstitial tissues and accumulation of lipids (low density lipoproteins) in various tissue. Thereby, impacting on the health of the workers [22]. In addition, there was an elevation in Serum Glutamic Oxaloacetic Transaminase (SGOT) and Serum Glutamic Pyruvic Transaminase (SGPT) levels in quarry workers which is also an indication of liver cell injury. This mirrors the study conducted by [23], where they observed a significant proportion of quarry workers had elevated levels of SGOT and SGPT compared to the control group. SGOT and SGPT are enzymes primarily found within liver cells, and their release into the bloodstream is indicative of hepatocellular damage [24]. The increase in Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP) levels among the quarry workers in this study, further underscores the potential hepatobiliary injury associated with exposure to quarry dust. This finding is in tandem with the result obtained by [25], where they found out that children living nearby quarry industries had exposure to high concentration of lead with concurrent increase in the levels of Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP), AST and ALT.

ALP is an enzyme present in bile ducts, and elevated levels can signify cholestasis or obstruction in the bile ducts. The elevation of ALP levels in the test groups suggests possible impairment in bile flow or liver function, indicating hepatobiliary dysfunction induced by exposure to quarry dust [26].

This study also revealed a significant decrease in the Packed Cell Volume (PCV) in the quarry workers compared to the control groups and mirrors the study by [21, 27]. The decline in PCV levels (33.04 ± 0.28 % in quarry workers versus 42.53 ± 0.33 % in control groups) can be attributed to factors such as chronic exposure to dust and particulate matter (nickel, lead and chromium) present in quarry environments. Inhalation of these particles can lead to respiratory issues, lung inflammation and fibrosis, which may subsequently impact the oxygen-carrying capacity of red blood cells, as reflected in the reduced PCV levels [21]. In addition, there was decrease in WBC count in the quarry workers. This reduction in WBC count suggests a compromised immune response among individuals exposed to quarry environments, which is consistent with the study of [28]. This suppression may lead to immune system dysregulation and increased susceptibility to respiratory infections and other illnesses [29]. Furthermore, the level of decrease in neutrophil count among the quarry workers is in agreement with the report of [21] and it makes them more vulnerable to bacterial infections [30, 31]. There was also an increase in Lymphocyte and eosinophil counts in the quarry workers. This is consistent with the study by [32, 33]. It means that there is a compensatory response to the diminished neutrophil count, as the body attempts to bolster its immune defenses against potential threats and allergens encountered in the quarry environments [33, 34]. These changes reflect the complex interplay between environmental factors, immune function, and overall health status of the workers, highlighting the need to protect the well-being of individuals working in or residing near quarry sites.

The two most important markers for evaluating kidney health are urea and creatinine, with higher values suggesting possible renal dysfunction. The results of this study indicate that the renal function of the workers is gradually being affected and necessary steps should be taken to mitigate the decline in the health of the quarry workers. [35], found that prolonged exposure to quarry dust led to increased levels of creatinine and urea significantly. The elevation of urea and creatinine levels can be ascribed to the presence of heavy metals and toxic substances in quarry dust, such as silica, asbestos, nickel, lead and cadmium, which can directly impair kidney function by causing nephrotoxicity [36]. Furthermore, prolonged exposure to high levels of noise in quarry environments can also have detrimental effects on kidney function. Chronic noise exposure has been linked to hypertension and cardiovascular diseases, which are risk factors for chronic kidney disease [37]. In addition, the physical demands of working in quarry environments, such as lifting of heavy objects and repetitive tasks, can contribute to dehydration and muscle breakdown, leading to an increase in urea and creatinine levels as a result of reduced renal perfusion and increased muscle turnover [38]. These findings underscore the importance of implementing measures to mitigate occupational hazards in quarry settings to protect the health and well-being of workers.

In our study, exposure to quarry environments has been shown to elicit various effects on urinary cell types. Firstly, inflammatory cells were identified in 75.0% of urinary cells within the quarry workers, a stark contrast to the absence of inflammatory cells in the control groups. This discrepancy highlights the inflammatory response triggered by exposure to quarry environments, likely due to inhalation of dust particles containing irritants or contaminants present in the quarry [28]. Moreover, tubule epithelial cells were prevalent in the urine of the majority (60.0%) of quarry workers. This suggests a potential impact on renal function and integrity, possibly stemming from exposure to toxins or pollutants inherent to quarry environments, which could disrupt tubular function and lead to cellular shedding into the urine [35]. Similarly, transitional epithelial cells were present in a significant portion (60.0%) of urinary samples in the quarry workers, indicating a disturbance in the urothelial integrity. This mirrors the report of [39]. Interestingly, the presence of calcium oxalate in urinary samples was not significantly different between quarry workers and control groups, suggesting that this parameter may not be directly influenced by quarry exposure. Calcium oxalate formation is primarily associated with dietary factors rather than environmental exposures [40]. Calcium oxalate crystals were identified in 40.0% of quarry workers, suggesting a propensity for urinary stone formation. Prolonged exposure to environmental factors prevalent in quarry settings, such as dust inhalation and dehydration, may contribute to the accumulation of calcium oxalate crystals in urine, increasing the risk of nephrolithiasis and renal complications. Hydration protocols, dietary modifications, and regular medical evaluations are essential for mitigating the incidence of urinary stone formation among quarry workers.

Yeast cells were infrequently observed in both quarry workers and control groups, with no significant difference between them. This suggests that yeast cells presence in urinary samples may be influenced by factors other than quarry exposure, such as systemic infections or lowered immune status [41]. Thus, regular health screenings for quarry workers using point of care urinary test kits and adequate ventilation, use of PPE, and adherence to occupational safety protocols are imperative to minimize the risk of urinary tract complications and improve the health of the quarry workers [42]. Quarry workers are advised to practice good hygiene and quarry owners should provide decent and adequate sanitation facilities; coupled with a reduction in exposure to quarry dust or heavy metal contaminants, the health of the workers will be enhanced.

Recommendations

The government should put in place policy that will implement and enforce tight dust control measures in quarry sites. Regular watering of quarry areas with the installation of ventilation systems that will help suck up the dust generated, and the enforcement of the use of appropriate PPE such as respirator is advised. The Government should also set up regular health monitoring and surveillance programs among quarry workers. As well as, ensure that quarry owners put in place strict hygiene protocols, regular sanitation inspections, and implementation of effective waste management practices in all the quarries and its surroundings.

6. Conclusion

The high concentration of heavy metals like lead, nickel, and chromium observed among the workers in the quarry site studied, has begun to have an effect on the health of the workers. There is a need for further intervention by health authorities and the quarry-site owners to avoid further deterioration in the health status of the workers in that area.

References

- [1] P. Bhattacharjee, A. Banerjee, and M. Bhattacharyya. Environmental pollution and its impact on human health. *Journal of Environmental Pollution*, 40(1):89–103, 2018.
- [2] R. Ali, T. Ahmad, and Z. Usman. Assessment of heavy metal contamination. *International Journal of Environmental Science*, 32(4): 451–468, 2019.
- [3] M. I. Castro-González and M. Méndez-Armenta. Toxicity of heavy metals in biological systems. *Toxicology Reports*, 5(1):12–28, 2008.
- [4] *Occupational Safety and Health administration By standard/1910.1051 App F-medical questionnaire (non-mandatory)*. Washington, DC USA, 2016. URL <http://www.osha.gov/laws-regs/regulations/standardnumber/1910/1910.1051AppF>.
- [5] A. A. Fischer, J. E. Laing, and J. E. Stoeckel. *Handbook for family planning operations research design*. Population Council, 2nd edition, 2008.
- [6] T. Olanrewaju, O. Afolabi, and O. Osibanjo. Prevalence of heavy metal toxicity in nigeria: A systematic review. *African Journal of Environmental Science*, 8(3):167–176, 2012.
- [7] Gcell. *Liver enzymes and biochemical analysis*. Retrieved from [details not provided], 2017.
- [8] Seamaty. *Fluid dynamics principles in auto-analyzer hematology testing*. Seamaty Diagnostics, 2022.
- [9] O. G. Avwioro. Histochemical uses of haematoxylin—a review. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Allied Sciences*, 2(1):22–34, 2002.
- [10] B. J. Bain. Blood cell morphology in health and disease. *British Journal of Haematology*, 196(2):274–289, 2022.
- [11] Agilent. *Estimation of heavy metals*. Retrieved from [details not provided], 2024.
- [12] H. Aloh, O. Aloh, C. Otuu, E. Shu, S. Inya-Agha, C. Obi-Ezeani, T. Halilu, and L. Ilouno. Occupational health hazards associated with continuous exposure to quarry activities among quarry workers in ebonyi state, south east geopolitical zone, nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Environmental Science, Toxicology and Food Technology (IOSR-JESTFT)*, 11:2319–2399, 2017. doi:10.9790/2402-1007XXXXX.
- [13] A. Aliyu and A. U. Shehu. Occupational hazards and safety measures among stone quarry workers in northern nigeria. *Nigerian Medical Practitioner*, 50, 2007. doi:10.4314/nmp.v50i2.28838.
- [14] N. Leon-Kabamba, N. R. Ngatu, B. A. Muzembo, S. Kakoma, N. Michel-Kabamba, B. Danuser, O. Luboya, and T. Hirao. Air quality in the working environment and respiratory health of female congolese stone quarry workers. *Tropical medicine and infectious disease*, 5(4):171, 2020.
- [15] D. F. Ahadzi, A. R. Afitiri, B. Ekumah, V. Kanatey, and A. Afedzi. Self-reported disease symptoms of stone quarry workers exposed to silica dust in ghana. *Health science reports*, 3(4):189, 2020.
- [16] S. Njaka, D. MohdYusoff, S. M. Anua, Y. C. Kueh, and C. O. Edeogu. Musculoskeletal disorders (msds) and their associated factors among quarry workers in nigeria: A cross-sectional study. *Heliyon*, 7(2):e06130, 2021.
- [17] M. Melodi. The effect of workers health on production in some selected quarries in southwestern nigeria. *FUOYE Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 2, 2017. doi:10.46792/fuoyejet.v2i1.55.
- [18] O. C. Ekhatior, T. Osobamiro, and E. O. Oloruntoba. Occupational exposure to heavy metals: An evaluation of the health implications for quarry workers. *Journal of Environmental Health Science*, 35(2):156–163, 2017.
- [19] T. Sanders, Y. Liu, V. Buchner, and P. B. Tchounwou. Neurotoxic effects and biomarkers of lead exposure: a review. *Reviews on environmental health*, 24(1):15–45, 2009.
- [20] P. Sharma, S. P. Singh, S. K. Parakh, and Y. W. Tong. Health hazards of hexavalent chromium (cr (vi)) and its microbial reduction. *Bioengineered*, 13(3):4923–4938, 2022.

- [21] E. Chukwurah, W. Nnaemeka, and C. Chinedum. Effects of quarry dust on some haematological parameters among workers at okposiumuoghara, ebonyi state -nigeria. *Saudi Journal of Biomedical Research*, 5:82–86, 2020.
- [22] N. Zawilla, F. Taha, and Y. Ibrahim. Liver functions in silica-exposed workers in egypt: possible role of matrix remodeling and immunological factors. *International journal of occupational and environmental health*, 20(2):146–156, 2014.
- [23] S. O. Osemwenkha, E. M. Onibokun, and M. E. Aghimien. Liver enzyme alterations in quarry workers exposed to heavy metals: A case study. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Health*, 22(3):215–223, 2013.
- [24] M. A. Kalas, L. Chavez, M. Leon, P. T. Taweeseedt, and S. Surani. Abnormal liver enzymes: A review for clinicians. *World journal of hepatology*, 13(11):1688–1698, 2021.
- [25] C. D. Ewenighi, A. Uchechukwu, I. Babatunde, O. Gabriel, O. Joel, O. Linus, E. Gladys, N. Uchechukwu, U. Harrison, M. Anojulu, and M. Amarachukwu. Enzymatic activities of glucose 6 phosphate dehydrogenase and some liver enzymes among quarry workers in umuoghara, ebonyi state- nigeria. *International Journal of Health Sciences and Research*, 2014.
- [26] M. D. Levitt, S. M. Hapak, and D. G. Levitt. Alkaline phosphatase pathophysiology with emphasis on the seldom-discussed role of defective elimination in unexplained elevations of serum alp - a case report and literature review. *Clinical and experimental gastroenterology*, 15:41–49, 2022.
- [27] O. Erhabor, B. I. Kebbe, Z. Isah, A. Isaac, Y. Nasiru, O. Marafa, H. Augustine, A. Buhari, O. Wase, A. Festus, B. Festus, M. Ikhuenbor, D. Abdullah, E. K. Muhammad, F. P. Uko, P. Udomah, A. Iwueke, O. Teddy, and O. Igbineweka. Effect of occupational exposure of cement dust on some haematological parameters of workers in a cement company in sokoto, nigeria. *International Journal of Medical Science and Health*, 1:21–25, 2013.
- [28] S. O. Onemu, E. I. Obeagu, A. A. Popoola, M. A. Osuntuyi, and C. N. Isibor. An assessment of the immune status of some stone quarry workers in ondo state, nigeria. *Medicine*, 103(2):e36969, 2024.
- [29] S. C. Hung, H. Y. Cheng, C. C. Yang, C. I. Lin, C. K. Ho, W. H. Lee, F. J. Cheng, C. J. Li, and H. Y. Chuang. The association of white blood cells and air pollutants-a population-based study. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 18(5):2370, 2021.
- [30] H. L. Malech, F. R. Deleo, and M. T. Quinn. The role of neutrophils in the immune system: an overview. *Methods in molecular biology (Clifton, N. J.)*, 1124:3–10, 2014.
- [31] S. D. Kobayashi, N. Malachowa, and F. R. DeLeo. Neutrophils and bacterial immune evasion. *Journal of innate immunity*, 10(5-6):432–441, 2018.
- [32] I. G. Jeong, K. S. Han, J. Y. Joung, W. S. Choi, S. S. Hwang, S. O. Yang, H. K. Seo, J. Chung, and K. H. Lee. Analysis of changes in the total lymphocyte and eosinophil count during immunotherapy for metastatic renal cell carcinoma: correlation with response and survival. *Journal of Korean medical science*, 22 Suppl(Suppl):S122–S128, 2007.
- [33] S. O. Maduka and E. D. Uchechukwu. Respiratory symptoms and blood eosinophil level in workers exposed to quarry dust in south-eastern nigeria. *Journal of Environmental and Occupational Science*, 3:175–180, 2014.
- [34] B. Alberts, A. Johnson, and J. Lewis. *Molecular Biology of the Cell*. Garland Science, New York, 4th edition, 2002. Lymphocytes and the cellular basis of adaptive immunity.
- [35] R. Bama, M. Sundaramahalingam, and N. Anand. Renal impairments in stone quarry workers. *Cureus*, 15(11):e48743, 2023.
- [36] M. Jaishankar, T. Tseten, N. Anbalagan, B. B. Mathew, and K. N. Beeregowda. Toxicity, mechanism and health effects of some heavy metals. *Interdisciplinary toxicology*, 7(2):60–72, 2014.
- [37] Y. J. Kim, W. J. Choi, S. Ham, S. K. Kang, and W. Lee. Association between occupational or environmental noise exposure and renal function among middle-aged and older korean adults: a cross-sectional study. *Scientific reports*, 11(1):24127, 2021.
- [38] W. G. Bongers, M. Alsady, T. Nijenhuis, D. M. Tulp, M. H. Eijsvogels, P. T. Deen, and T. E. Hopman. Impact of acute versus prolonged exercise and dehydration on kidney function and injury. *Physiological reports*, 6(11):e13734, 2018.
- [39] N. V. Jafari and J. L. Rohn. The urothelium: a multi-faceted barrier against a harsh environment. *Mucosal immunology*, 15(6):1127–1142, 2022.
- [40] S. R. Khan. Reactive oxygen species, inflammation and calcium oxalate nephrolithiasis. *TranslAndrolUrol*;3(3):256-276, 2014.
- [41] S. R. Shing, A. R. Ramos, K. A. Patras, A. M. Riestra, S. McCabe, V. Nizet, and A. Coody. The fungal pathogen candida albicans promotes bladder colonization of group b streptococcus. *Front. Cell. Infect. Microbiol.*, 9:437, 2020.
- [42] B. H. Oladeinde, R. Omoregie, M. Olley, and J. A. Anunibe. Urinary tract infection in a rural community of nigeria. *North American journal of medical sciences*, 3(2):75–77, 2011.